

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL 1: Figures and table

FIG. S1. Strict consensus tree (L=221) of the most parsimonious trees from ITS. Numbers above branches correspond to jackknife support above 64%. In the black box the new species.

FIG. S2. Single most parsimonious tree (L=27) from the plastid *ndhF-rpl32* spacer region. Numbers above branches correspond to jackknife support above 64%. In the black box the new species.

